

spin-spin coupling in the interacting vanadium atoms and the exchange interaction is of the antiferromagnetic type with singlet ground state^{2,3}.

The low temperature magnetic and electron spin resonance studies of the complexes are progressing and details will be reported in due course. The corresponding oxomolybdenum(V), oxotungsten(V) and copper(II) complexes are also being studied in order to compare the magnetic exchange behaviour of these $S = \frac{1}{2}$ systems. The syntheses of coordination complexes of various other transition and non-transition metal ions with I are being carried out.

Acknowledgement

The authors are grateful to the Department of Atomic Energy (Government of India) and faculty research fund of Regional Engineering College, Kurukshetra for financial support of this research. They thank Dr. S. Banerjee for experimental assistance.

References

1. J. A. BERTRAND, J. L. BREECH, A. R. KALYANARAMAN, G. J. LONG and W. A. BAKER, JR., *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, **92**, 5233; W. E. HATFIELD and R. WHYMAN, *Transition Metal Chemistry*, 1969, **5**, 47; D. J. HODGSON, *Progress Inorganic Chemistry*, 1975, **19**, 1.
2. A. SYAMAL, *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1975, **16**, 309.
3. A. P. GINSBERG, R. C. SHERWOOD and E. KOUBECK, *J. Inorg. Nuclear Chem.*, 1967, **29**, 353.
4. A. P. GINSBERG, E. KOUBECK and H. J. WILLIAMS, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1966, **5**, 1656.
5. A. SYAMAL and L. J. THERRIOT, *J. Coord. Chem.*, 1973, **2**, 193.
6. A. T. T. HSIEH, R. M. SHEAHAM and B. O. WEST, *Aust. J. Chem.*, 1975, **28**, 885.
7. J. SELBIN, *Chem. Rev.*, 1965, **65**, 153; *Coord. Chem. Rev.*, 1966, **1**, 293.

Dissociation Constants of 1, 10-Phenanthroline and its Iron(II) Complex in Ethanol and Water Mixtures

(Mrs.) A. BHATTACHARYYA and S. C. LAHIRI

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani,
Kalyani, Nadia, West Bengal

Manuscript received 28 September 1977, revised 14 February
1978, accepted 26 April 1978

In order to explore the role of the solvents on the dissociation constants of the complexes, we studied the dissociation constants of the following 'iso-electric' equilibria in ethanol+water mixtures. (Containing 8-87 wt% of ethanol)

The thermodynamics of reaction (1) have been reported. We report in this communication the equilibrium constants for reactions (2) and (3) in ethanol+water mixtures.

Methods and Materials

The purification of the solvent, the preparation of ferrous-ammonium-sulphate and 1, 10-phenanthroline solutions, the determination of the weight percentages of the organic solvents in the mixed solvents and their dielectric constants were done in the way described before¹⁻³.

The chemicals used were of G.R. grade. Double-distilled water was used for preparing the solutions.

The organic solvent I has been found to have little effect on the absorption maximum of ferroin which is 510 nm. Under our experimental conditions, FePh_3^{2+} has been assumed to be the sole species formed without any FePh^{2+} and FePh_3^{2+} .

The molar absorptivities ϵ 's of ferroin were determined at 500, 510 and 520 nms from the measurement of absorbances of solutions containing more than 10 fold excess of ligand to known amounts of ferrous ion where complete conversion of Fe^{2+} to FePh_3^{2+} took place.

For the determination of stability constants of ferroin in mixed solvents, absorbances of solutions containing different amounts of Fe^{2+} ion and 1, 10-phenanthroline (Concn. range $8-20 \times 10^{-6} M$) were measured at 500, 510 and 520 nms. The pHs ranged from 2.60-3.80.

For the calculation of equilibrium constants for the reactions (2) and (3), the average values of the complex obtained from absorbance measurements and ϵ values at three wavelengths were taken.

Spectrophotometric readings were taken with a Beckman DU Spectrophotometer maintained at 25°. The pH-meter readings were taken with a Cambridge-bench type battery operated pH-meter.

Results

In mixed solvents, the activity coefficients change due to

(i) Salt effect (f_i), (ii) Medium effect (f_m). Salt effect may be eliminated by working in very dilute solutions so that

$f_i \rightarrow 1$, i.e. $f_{\text{Fe}^{2+}} = f_{\text{FePh}_3^{2+}}$ and $f_{\text{H}^+} = f_{\text{PhH}^+}$. This enables us to get an idea regarding 'medium effect' with which we are concerned in our studies in mixed solvents. Furthermore, addition of inert electrolyte or increase in the concentrations of reactions would lead to further complications due to

- (a) ion-association,
- (b) Solute-solvent interactions and preferential solvation of ions in mixed solvents.

Considering these facts, the present work has been carried out in solutions of the order of $10^{-3}M$ (ionic strengths were of the order of 4.0×10^{-4} to $3.3 \times 10^{-3}M$).

The thermodynamic equilibrium constant K_a for reaction (2) has been calculated from

$$(\text{PhH}^+) = (\text{Ph})_{\text{total}} - 3(\text{FePh}_3^{2+}) - (\text{Ph}) \quad \dots (4)$$

$$pK_T = \text{pH} + \log \frac{(\text{PhH}^+)}{(\text{Ph})} \quad \dots (5)$$

$$\text{and } (\text{Fe}^{2+})_{\text{free}} = (\text{Fe}^{2+})_{\text{total}} - (\text{FePh}_3^{2+}) \quad \dots (6)$$

We prefer to use the theoretical values of H^+ ion concentrations in calculating the K -values in view of increasing discrepancy of the theoretical and experimental values of H^+ ion concentrations (as measured pH -metrically using appropriate correction⁴) as the percentage of organic solvent increases. This is expected in mixed solvents with ions of different charge types due to

(1) liquid-junction potential of uncertain magnitude,

(2) change in sensitivity of the electrode,

(3) solute-solvent interactions and consequent medium effect.

The dissociation constant for the reaction (3) in different solvents are given by

$$K = K_a \times K_T^2 \quad \dots (7)$$

Discussions

The pK values for the reactions (1), (2) and (3) at different percentages of mixed solvents are given in Table 1.

actions in mixed solvents with ions and complexes of higher valence types may have influence on the equilibrium constants. Considering the limitations, the results can be regarded to be in good agreement.

In consistence with the previous observations it has been found that solute-solvent interactions are the major terms to explain the solvent-effect,^{1-3,5} the electrostatic terms being of minor importance due to 'isoelectric' nature of the reactions. Greater solubility of 1, 10-phenanthroline in mixed solvents and the differences in the solvational properties of H^+ , PhH^+ , FePh_3^{2+} and Fe^{2+} are partly responsible for the change in pK values. However, the nature of solvation are not clear but it is likely that Fe^{2+} and H^+ ions would be preferentially solvated by water molecule compared to PhH^+ and FePh_3^{2+} due to bigger ion-sizes.

The pK_T values for reaction (1) show a minimum in the region 65-75 wt.% of organic solvents by spectrophotometry. The pK_a values for the reaction (2) are peculiar showing abnormality near about 25 and 54 wt.% of alcohol. For reaction (3), the pK -values decrease as the alcohol content increases. Slight deviation is noted near about 65 wt.%. The 'correction factor' were maximal near about 65 wt.%. The changes in molar absorptivities with increasing alcohol though interesting but cannot be correlated with the other data obtained.

It is known that $\Delta \text{pK} = \Delta \text{pK}_{\text{el}} + \Delta \text{pK}_{\text{nonel}}$. But for the 'isoelectric' reactions, $\Delta \text{pK}_{\text{el}}$ may be assumed to be almost constant as a first approximation throughout the solvent composition. Thus, the change in pK represent primarily the change in $\Delta \text{pK}_{\text{nonel}}$ which is governed to a large extent by solute-solvent, in interactions and solvent basicity

TABLE-1

Wt. % of ethanol	Mole-fraction of ethanol	$1/\epsilon \times 10^3$	pK_T for reacn. (1)		Extinction Coefficients of Ferrioin			pK_a for reacn.(2)	pK for reacn.(3)
			Spectro-photomet.	pH -metry	500 nm	510 nm.	520 nm		
0	0.000	1.27	5.05 ^a	—	—	—	—	5.95	20.50 ^a
8.0	0.033	1.35	4.90	4.82	10578(±15)	10780(±15)	9792(±15)	5.90	19.76
16.4	0.071	1.42	4.75	4.70	10760	10920	9890	5.12	19.22
25.3	0.117	1.53	4.50	4.41	11500	11710	10540	4.96	18.59
34.4	0.170	1.71	4.34	4.27	11760	11910	10820	5.54	18.35
44.0	0.235	1.90	4.05	4.03	11600	11780	10510	5.21	17.30
54.1	0.315	2.14	3.82	3.89	11170	11500	11020	5.03	16.70
64.7	0.418	2.45	3.68	3.77	10810	11260	10640	5.61	16.92
76.0	0.554	2.92	3.62	3.70	10610	11000	10460	5.44	16.54
87.6	0.754	3.41	3.70	—	10600	10956	10890	5.03	16.13

The plots of pK values against mole-fraction and $1/\epsilon$ give linear plots nearly up to 65 per cent. of organic solvent within the limits of experimental error.

It is to be noted that slight error in the measurement of H^+ ions (± 0.04) will have profound effect on K_a and K . Moreover, the solute-solvent inter-

which are probably maximum in the region of 60-80 wt.% of ethanol.

Acknowledgement

The authors thank the U. G. C. for awarding a Junior Research Fellowship to (Mrs.) A. Bhattacharyya.

References

1. S. C. LAHIRI, G. BISWAS and S. ADITYA, *Thermochim. Acta.*, 1977, **9**, 865.
2. D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *Anal. Chim. Acta.*, 1975, **79**, 885.
3. D. K. HAZRA and S. C. LAHIRI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1976, **53**, 787.
4. S. C. LAHIRI and S. ADITYA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1974, **51**, 819.
5. R. G. BATES, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1971, **29**, 1.
6. S. C. LAHIRI, and S. ADITYA, *Z. Physik. Chem (N.F.)*, 1964, **41**, 173.

Studies on Some Mixed-ligand Complexes of Tin Tetrachloride

T. N. SRIVASTAVA, P. C. SRIVASTAVA and O. C. SINGH
Chemistry Department, Lucknow University Lucknow.
Manuscript received 27 June 1977 : accepted 24 April 1978

In continuation to our studies on mixed-ligand complexes¹ we wish to report synthesis and characterisation of a few more hitherto unknown complexes of similar general formula $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{LL}'$ (L = dimethyl formamide (DMF), dimethyl acetamide (DMA), dimethyl propionamide (DMP), or diphenylformamide (DPF); L' = pyridine N-oxide (PyO) or lutidine N-oxide (TNO)). Possible structure of the complexes is suggested.

Experimental

Materials: Commercially available tin tetrachloride was used after distillation. DMF, DMA, DMP, DPF, PyO and LNO were obtained from Fischer Scientific U. S. A. and used as such.

Preparation of complexes: The mixed-ligand complexes were prepared according to one of the following methods:

(i) Displacement reaction:

In a representative experiment a solution of 2 m moles of $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot 2\text{DMF}$ in 10 ml. acetonitrile was treated with an equimolar quantity of PyO in the same solvent. The mixture was refluxed for about two hours and the excess solvent was distilled off. The residual solution on treatment with diethyl ether yielded a white crystalline solid which was filtered, washed and dried in vacuum.

(ii) Adduct formation:

A solution of 5 m moles of tin tetrachloride in 10 ml carbon tetrachloride was treated with an equimolar mixture of DMF and PyO (5 m mole each) in 10 ml of the same solvent with constant stirring. The precipitated white crystalline solid was identical to that obtained through displacement reaction.

The experimental results are collected in Table 1.

Results and Discussion

The newly synthesised compounds are white crystalline solid having poor solubility in organic solvents. They are non-electrolytes, thermally stable and unaffected by atmospheric moisture and oxygen.

The IR spectral data show a distinct negative shift of the C=O stretching frequency and a slight positive shift of the NCO bending mode from their position in the free ligands, in agreement to the observations of previous workers²⁻⁵, and indicate the coordination from the oxygen atom of the amide molecule to the tin atom. The presence of coordinated N=O ligands through the oxygen atom is indicated from the following⁶⁻⁹:

(a) The N=O str. mode around $1185 \pm 5 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ is distinctly shifted to lower frequency region as compared to that in the free bases.

(b) The N=O bending mode appears at $832 \pm 3 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in the complexes. Its location is not very different from that in the corresponding bases which is in agreement to the observations and explanations of several previous workers.

TABLE I—ANALYTICAL RESULTS AND IR ABSORPTION FREQUENCIES (cm^{-1}) FOR $\text{SnCl}_4 \cdot \text{LL}'$

L	L'	Sn	Analysis % obs. (calcd.)			N	IR absorption frequencies (cm^{-1})				
			C	H	N		Amide I band $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\delta(\text{N}-\text{C}=\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{N}-\text{O})$	$\delta(\text{N}-\text{O})$	$\nu(\text{C}-\text{H})$
DMF	PyO	26.80	20.30	2.82	6.40	1610 m	670 vs	1180 s	830 vs	780 vs	400 m
		(27.71)	(20.21)	(2.81)	(6.31)						330 m
DMA	PyO	26.40	24.62	3.38	6.50	1610 m	675 vs	1180 m	830 vs	780 vs	390 m
		(26.80)	(24.38)	(3.19)	(6.25)						335 m
DMP	PyO	25.60	28.20	3.78	6.00	1620 vs	670 s	1190 m	835 sh	775 vs	390 vs
		(25.28)	(28.02)	(3.80)	(5.98)						310 m
DPF	PyO	21.90	39.30	3.44	5.50	1615 m	690 m	1190 m	830 vs	775 s	390 vs
		(21.58)	(39.04)	(3.80)	(5.38)						320 m
DMF	LNO	26.00	26.28	3.80	6.80	1610 m	710 m	1185 s	832 m	790 s	410 w
		(26.04)	(26.20)	(3.58)	(6.59)						380 s
DMA	LNO	25.60	28.03	3.58	5.58	1615 m	700 m	1190 m	835 m	790 s	400 m
		(25.28)	(28.02)	(3.80)	(5.90)						380 m
DMP	LNO	23.60	31.50	4.80	5.50	1620 m	680 m	1182 s	832 m	780 s	390 m
		(23.70)	(31.19)	(4.58)	(5.00)						320 w
DPF	LNO	20.80	41.60	3.60	4.60	1612 m	690 vs	1180 m	834 vs	790 vs	410 w
		(20.48)	(41.38)	(3.48)	(4.80)						375 m